

Regulation of Meso Trajectories in the National Innovation System

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Abstract: The meso trajectory is considered as a sequential process of performing core functions on the phases of the development of the national innovation system (NIS). It constitutes a three-phase process. They describe emergence (origination), diffusion (adoption, adaptation and assimilation) and retention of a new successful rule (innovation). The study focuses on two groups of factors of these phases. The first is external factors whose action is manifested in the existence of high risks and uncertainties distributed over the stages of the meso trajectory. The second group occurs within the meso populations of the trajectory. The actors of these populations shape the group. Regarding the first group of factors, two conclusions are drawn. First, government policy that aims to mitigate inherent risks and uncertainties must be dual. It means that, on the one hand, the policy should provide compensation for a part of the uncertainties and risks inherent in innovation activity, and, on the other hand, make the actors carry some significant portion of risks themselves. Secondly, if the policy is intended for regulating the effects of externalities (e.g. technological spillover) on different phases of the trajectory, then its task is to maintain the necessary balance of their influences on NIS core functions on the adjacent phases of the trajectory. The paper introduces the concept of factor-forming populations. The action of factor-forming populations contributes to the dynamics of meso trajectories and performance of NIS functions at the phases of the trajectory. In the study, such populations are carrying the attributes of factors having a significant impact on meso trajectories. The public policy must weaken a factor-forming population with a negative impact on performing the NIS functions and reinforce those that have a positive effect on them. If factor-forming populations demonstrate both positive and negative influence on the trajectory, the policy should assist in strengthening useful parameters and smoothing harmful their behavioural models. The modern dynamics of some graduations of the factor-forming populations are analysed for Russia.

Keywords: meso trajectories, phases, populations, functions of innovation system, incentives and disincentives, public policy

1. Introduction

The possibilities for applying traditional approaches (including neoclassical theory and theory of growth) and their tools to the analysis of innovation systems are mostly limited (Lundvall and Johnson, 1994; Golichenko 2016). Frequently, the main conceptual statements of these approaches contradict the fundamental properties of the National innovation system (NIS) and its actors' characteristics. For example, it is not always possible to attribute NIS actors to the economic agents, especially in cases when gaining economic benefits is not their objective. Actors are not often representative as agents in the economic mainstream and not always benefit-oriented in short-term and sometimes medium-term perspectives. The actor of the NIS is often considered as decision-making under bounded rationality.

At present, the concept of a national innovation system covers all the major components of the innovation process, including organisational, social, political, and economic factors. Researchers and decision makers widely use this concept at the regional, national and international levels (Edquist, 2006; Sharif, 2006). At the same time, many authors indicated as one of the main disadvantages of the NIS approach that it lacks bridges between the macro and micro that are inherent in mainstream economic research. According to Edquist, when moving to a macro level, the innovation system is regarded as a single entity without breaking out into the subprocesses and their actors (Edquist, 2006, p. 186). Here it may just be noted that in the current practice of NIS research, this approach often looks quite static. Miettinen says that the NIS approach "is poorly connected to ... a dynamic way of thinking" (Miettinen, 2013, p. 35).

The neo-evolutionary theory (NET), which has arisen relatively recently (Dopfer and Potts, 2014), is free from these shortcomings). Therefore, to eliminate the shortages and achieve a new quality analysis of innovation development, it seems reasonable to integrate the achievements of this theory and the NIS approach. The following facts indicate that these approaches are compatible.

Like the NIS approach (Freeman, 1987; Lundvall, 1992; Nelson, 1993; Metcalfe, 1995), knowledge is the central category of the NET. According to (Dopfer et al., 2015), the "bit" of knowledge serves as the nuclear element of evolutionary economics. This bit is considered as a particular rule in the NET (Dopfer et al. 2004; Dopfer 2012; Dopfer and Potts 2008). In neo-evolutionary economics as well as in the national innovation system, the emphasis is on the consideration of new knowledge (rules). The NET and NIS actors are knowledge holders; their activity is associated with the generation and use of creative knowledge

In the NET, the carriers of the same (rather complex) knowledge-rule are combined into a population. It is called a meso population. Therefore, the couple of rule-meso population is taken as a single object called the meso-unit in the NET. The dynamic process of the development of meso-units determines a meso trajectory (Dopfer et al., 2004) or market trajectory (Bleda, 2013). As a result of passing through the trajectory, meso population grows from one holder (entrepreneur or technology supplier) of a new technological knowledge/rule to a population. The meso trajectory consists of the subsequent phases of the development of a complex rule. They are emergence (origination), diffusion (adaptation and assimilation) and retention of the rule.

As for the NIS approach, it is worthwhile to note that although here the emphasis is not explicitly made on dynamics, the main (core) functions of NIS processes take after the abovementioned characteristics of the meso trajectory phases. These functions of NIS can be established from the existing definitions of the national innovation system (see, for example, Freeman 1987; Lundvall 1992; Nelson 1993; Patel and Pavitt 1994; Metcalfe 1995). One can easily see the following ones: creation (generation), storage, distribution (diffusion or transfer) and effective economic use of knowledge (its commercialization). The similarity of the content of NIS functions and phases of meso trajectories is obvious. However, it is worth point out d the task of knowledge retaining is absent among the NIS core functions. Maybe this task needs combining with such a score NIS function as storage. The newly expanded role, on the one hand, ensures the corresponding institutionalisation of the technological regime. Thanks to the task, technological innovation is accepted by a significant number of users and the markets where it is realised become mass. On the other hand, the excessive conservation of the technological regime can generate a track effect slowing down the technological development of the country.

Consequently, the meso trajectory can be presented as a sequential process of performing core functions 0 on the different phases.

In the first phase (Meso 1) of the evolutionary trajectory, the emergence of ideas adopted by a group (meso population) and their first actualisation occur at the micro level. Following Schumpeter's point of view on entrepreneurial activity (Schumpeter 1942), this phase is dealing with an active entrepreneur showing ingenuity under conditions of uncertainty and risks. Moreover, this entrepreneur is able not only to overcome scepticism proposing a new rule, but he also can take a fresh look at the well-known rule. Besides, he may even find sources of funding for his activities to build a mechanism for the implementation of the new or updated rule (Teece et al., 1997). If successful, the targeted actions of the economic agent may change the existing boundaries of entrepreneurial activity and perhaps alter the essence of this activity. At the same time, as current practice shows, a discoverer or carrier of a new rule can be not only the manufacturer of new goods and services but sometimes a consumer reveals demand for products and services not previously produced (Earl and Potts 2004).

In the second phase (Meso 2) of the evolutionary trajectory, the adoption and adaptation of the novelty at the local level, i.e. diffusion of innovation and its support in the economic system, take place. The macro-effect of the phase is the beginning of the destruction of the prior coordination and re-coordination caused by reformatting the behaviour of actors. It is a result of the spread of the new rule. This process of the institutionalisation is an essence of the Schumpeterian approach to economic evolution.

Meso 3 is the boundary and final phase at which the retainability and replication of the rule and at least the preservation of its carriers occur, and the establishment of a new macro-order takes place. The phase is a well-structured state in which innovation is already introduced into the system and metastable structures provide the basis of the order. Profit is at a reasonable level, uncertainties have completely transformed into risks; actors' expectations are based on ongoing experiments and comparisons of their results. Technology is widely initialised and adopted by a significant number of users, and markets using the technology are transforming into large-scale ones.

Certain factors influence the development of the phases of the meso trajectories. They can be combined into two groups. The first of them are the factors that are shaped outside of the meso populations at the corresponding trajectory phase. The second is formed inside of the meso populations of the evolutionary trajectory.

In the first, we include two following categories of risks and uncertainties: 1) inherent in innovation; 2) associated with threats of adverse externalities of technological spillover. They stem from an external environment and determine anti-stimuli for the actors' activities in meso populations.

The second group comprises the factors whose elements are moulded by some actors of meso populations. The actors that fall into a factor forming population are holders of the attributes of a distinguished factor. Actions of these populations may promote or inhibit the phases of meso trajectories.

In light of the previous, one of the tasks of public policy is to mitigate the risks and uncertainties. In this study, we do not take into account such external factors of innovation activities as components of framework conditions. The regulation of influence of the factor-forming populations on the trajectory is the second problem of the NIS. The present study attempts to crystallize the mentioned groups of factors and some measures of public policy to regulate their actions. It means that actors cluster the group (populations) of factor characteristic carriers according to the factors.

In this context, it is worthwhile to note that public policy on the evolutionary trajectory differs significantly from the traditional economic, particularly, industrial policy in its goals and role-playing behaviour of the government. Under the general economic (industrial) policy, government actions usually aim at a structural transformation of the economy as a whole (Bianchi and Labory 2006), economic development and growth of manufacturing and other types of production (see also Graham 1994). Below, the term "public or government policy" is referred to government regulatory action to facilitate the drivers of a country's development and eliminate barriers (OECD 2005) for performing core functions of NIS. Moreover, in contrast to the traditional theory, the government has bounded rationality and is only one of the possible participants in the processes of destroying futile trends of the trajectory and searching and implementing new ones.

And finally, one must take into account that these government's efforts cannot be expected to succeed without solving the problem of encouraging actors to perform NIS functions as well as regulating the activities of factor-forming populations at different NIS levels. This paper is devoted to the consideration of these problems.

2. External factors for meso trajectories: risks and uncertainty emerging in environment

For actors, the activity on the phases of the meso trajectory has two sides. The first is positive, and it is related to the possible economic benefits of innovation. These benefits generate incentives for the activity of NIS actors. The second is negative, and it is determined by the presence of strong disincentives to perform core NIS function to get these benefits. The high risk and uncertainty of actors' activity lay the groundwork of the disincentives. Consequently, the stimulus must outweigh the anti-stimulus in order this activity takes place.

The disincentives are unevenly distributed along the meso trajectory. If the proposed innovation is radically new, then the most significant uncertainty of positive results in the innovation activity occurs in the Meso 1 phase. However, if the successful development of the innovation processes provides the transition of the meso trajectory to the Meso 2, then calibrated risks of getting innovative results will replace the uncertainty.

Risks and uncertainties in the NIS on the trajectory can be conditionally clustered into two groups (Golichenko 2013). The first group includes uncertainties and risks that are "natural", i.e. intrinsic and inherent, in actors' activity. Their presence, especially on the early stages of technology creation, does not make firms eager to invest in innovation and support them. At the same time, if framework conditions are x-optimal (Niosi 2002), then the particular measures of public support aimed directly at compensating for the anti-stimulus for innovation begin to play a significant role.

Government, as a partner of an entrepreneur, tries to diminish the "natural" risks and uncertainties at initial phases of the trajectory. On the other hand, the government's steps may induce NIS actors to act as free riders and encourage them to receive rental income from the corresponding financial help of the government. The government to avoid this phenomenon should strive for such conditions that make actors accept a significant part of the innovative risks and uncertainties. In other words, dualism has to be inherent in government policy.

The dualism means that the domains of public policy will not only compensate for the system of anti-stimulus but also force the participants of the NIS to take on significant shares of uncertainties and risks. One of the methods of actors' compulsion (Golichenko, 2017) to this sharing is an international competition. As for the mitigation of "natural" or inherent risks, cooperation among enterprises as well as their collaboration with organisations of the government and higher education sectors are essential to smooth the risks.

The existence of the second group of risks and uncertainties can be associated with threats of adverse externalities or spillover (Golichenko and Samovoleva, 2015) on the meso trajectory. For example, if an actor was successful at Meso1, he succeeded in such a NIS function of an economic application of new knowledge.

Nevertheless, the actor would not receive the full benefit from his innovations without sharing it with competitors, if the spread of innovations, i.e. fulfilment of such a core function as diffusion, took place due to the effect of technological spillover (the unauthorised use of these innovations).

This effect often does not arouse the actors' desire for creating innovations. An actor-innovator to avoid this effect could use substantial isolationist barriers protecting his new innovative knowledge (Peteraf 1993, Peteraf and Barney 2003). The durable protection of intellectual property supported by the government can act as such a barrier. However, it must be borne in mind that powerful isolationist barriers may hinder the diffusion of innovations. Then such an essential function of the NIS as the dissemination of new technological knowledge can be disrupted. The phenomenon may also sometimes impede the development of the new rules laid down in radical innovations as well as introducing innovative changes in related fields of activity.

In summary, the public policy, the purpose of which is to shape the actors' inducement, should include the following objectives:

1. holding dual policy measures of policy measures, on the one hand, to compensate uncertainties (on Meso 1) and risks (on Meso 2 and Meso 3) and, on the other hand, to force NIS actors to deal with these uncertainties and risks taking on with them through the trajectory;
2. maintaining a balance of performing various NIS functions at different phases of the meso trajectory.

3. Internal factors for meso trajectories: populations as holders of factor attributes

In addition to the mentioned above factors, such as uncertainties and risks, the factors formed among the meso populations themselves play a significant role in the evolutionary trajectory. They are constructed by some members of the populations in the course of their activities along the meso trajectory.

Such factors can include:

- Resource capability NIS actors, i.e. their provision of primary resources (in particular, their shortage or redundancy).
- Firms' forms of ownership
- The technological complexity of innovative products.
- Spatial distribution of innovation processes and actors.
- Technological paradigms in the economy.
- Absorption capacity and its distribution among actors.

For every factor, we can divide the sample of actors, innovative-active industrial enterprises into the populations in such a way that a member of every emerging population will be a carrier of at least one of factor attributes. It allows us to establish a correspondence between the features of the factor and sets of their holders. Let us designate the population consisting of actors-carriers of the attribute of a given factor as

"a factor forming population". In other words, the holders of the same attribute of the particular factor can be presented as the relevant factor-forming population.

As an example, consider a factor such as resource availability or resource provision of enterprises. Let us assume that this level can be low, medium and high. According to these gradations, the set of industrial enterprises is broken down into factor-forming populations of small-, medium- and large-sized enterprises. For instance, these populations can include the following groups:

- Small enterprises up to 99 employees.
- Enterprises with the number of employees from 300 to 499.
- Large enterprises with employees between 500 and 9999, and above 10000 personals.

The ranges of employees that are available for these enterprises are attributes of such the factor. It worth noting that enterprises within these specified factor-forming populations are not distinguishable; that is, at this level of consideration, the group of enterprises can be considered as homogeneous unless otherwise specified. In this context, for given attributes or gradations of the factor, the analysis deals with homogeneous populations (groups of enterprises).

Now, let us look at another example of factor-forming populations along the evolutionary trajectory. They are related to such a factor as forms of ownership of NIS actors. The sample of actors (e.g. innovative industrial enterprises) can be subdivided into factor-forming populations according to the gradations of ownership the actors are belonging. The structure of gradations can obey a hierarchy. In the case of Russia, it can be presented as follows. At the macro level of the hierarchy, ownership has two attributes, such as Russian and non-Russian property.

Further, Russian property should be presented as public and non-public ones. The former has two gradations: federal property and ownership of Russian Federation subjects. The following features can classify the latter as follows: municipal property, the private one, the property of consumer cooperatives, ownership of public and religious organisations, mixed (private and state-owned) property. And last but not the least the non-Russian property that includes foreign and joint ownership. The private one, the property of consumer cooperatives, ownership of public and religious organisations, mixed (private and state-owned) property. And last but not the least the non-Russian property that includes foreign and joint ownership.

This just mentioned set of features can be regarded as finite; that is, it is not subject to further division. It means that organisations grouped by the listed attributes are taken as homogeneous regarding the corresponding form of ownership. In this context, it is worthwhile to point out that in other cases, for instance, considering the technological complexity of innovative products, the hierarchy of attributes of the factor must be deeper and homogeneous factor-forming populations of higher hierarchy level have to be split into subpopulations on the next lower level.

Besides, it is worth noticing that according mentioned above examples, for every attribute of the established factor the factor-forming population, there is an actor-carrier, i.e. the set of factor-forming populations is complete. There is atomicity of the factor attribute distribution. It means that no actor of the factor-forming population could be a carrier of two attributes at once. The property of the atomicity implies that the factor-forming populations are not overlapping. In other words, we associate the factor with disjoint subsets of the sample and every subset, i.e. a population, has carried only one attribute.

Now let us turn our attention to the analysis of dynamics of populations forming attributes such as the resource capacities and forms of ownership in Russia. Besides, we will try to determine measures of policies addressed to the improvement of their positive influence on an evolutionary trajectory and reduce the negative impact on it.

3.1 The resource capacity

The characteristics of evolutionary trajectory depend substantially on the level of common resources available for enterprises, i.e. sizes of enterprises.

In particular, for innovation-active enterprises of Russia, representatives of populations of small dimension, that is, small and medium-sized enterprises have a significant share of innovative products in their sales. It is worth pointing out that although in 2010-2012 some populations of large enterprises showed growth of this indicator at times, many of them were apparent outsiders. They had had shares of innovative products in sales well below the those of three out of four populations of small and medium-sized businesses. Only the population of enterprises with employment between 1000 and 4999 people managed to exceed the level for small and medium-sized businesses populations.

In 2012 - 2015, the situation repeated: three out of four resource-rich populations had the lower meaning of the indicator compared to three resource-poor populations. By contrast, it is worth noting that, despite the steady outsider's positions of the large enterprises' populations, they managed to reduce the gap with the leadership positions of small and medium-sized enterprises on Meso 2.

Here, not the last role could be played by the circumstance that the state-owned enterprises belonging to the populations of large enterprises were forced to accept the special innovation development programs (IDP) in which the share of innovative products in sales was drafted from above by the government. According to the plans, the enterprises must be answerable to the government for achieving the target value of this indicator. This responsibility, posing significant risks of over-statement and falsification of this indicator value for large state-owned enterprises, may trigger the sharp increase of its meaning in these years.

It is worthwhile to point out that in the country as a whole the level and dynamics of indicators of the innovation activity scale and economic efficiency along the meso trajectories continue to be almost wholly established by the populations of large enterprises due to their dominance in the economy. However, as just mentioned, the indicators of large enterprises often point to a lack of their activity along evolution trajectories.

It is essential to overcome the innovative passivity of large enterprises and increase the groups of small and medium innovative business to find a way out of the situation. Furthermore, policy measures are needed to constitute a framework of conditions in the field of entrepreneurship. It concerns, in the first place, reducing regulatory and administrative barriers and developing and providing competitive environments in markets.

The populations of small and medium enterprises had primary positive innovative attributes. The populations need increasing and supporting by the state. The critical task of public innovation policy is to establish conditions for the rapid growth and prosperity of new firms based on one technology on the meso trajectories. The urgency of the issue is determined by the fast development of outsourcing processes on the final stages of R&D as well as the traditional disability of large firms to implement quickly new methods of doing business and introducing quite drastic changes in production and delivery methods.

3.2 Forms of ownership

The form of property has a substantial impact on the behaviour of the firm and its development and affect the choice of organisational model, management and innovation activity of the firm. The enterprises of private and mixed ownership demonstrate the most significant influence on the overall situation in innovation. In 2015, the number of privately-owned enterprises was 47% (versus 52% in 2006) among innovation active industrial enterprises on Meso 2, along with that the mixed-owned ones consisted 11% (versus 17% in 2006). Consequently, both populations concentrate about 65–70% of the general (human and material) resources of innovation. The next in importance to the influence were the populations of the federal property (15-17% in the number of enterprises and quantities of resources) and joint ownership (7-10%).

For many years, private ownership has not been a leader in entrepreneurial activity in innovation. In particular, the organisations of this form of property has been significantly behind those of federal property. It concerns a share of innovative products in sales. Moreover, according to this indicator, the gap between these forms of ownership has increased dramatically in recent years. Two circumstances can explain that increase. First, as mentioned above, federally owned enterprises had adopted innovative development plans with a commitment to enhancing innovative products in sales dramatically. Secondly, the government had undertaken intensive financial interventions to support state-owned enterprises.

According to the Center for Strategic Research, within the framework of the IDP, there was a significant increase in funding for the state-owned corporations and companies with state participation leading in high-

tech industries in 2011-2016. In 2016, the gross expenditures of the state budget on R&D in these companies reached 1.7% of GDP (Idrisov et al. p.12). As a result, the spending on technological innovations of these companies increased more than 20 times. It would seem that this surge in subsidies should drastically enlarge the scale of innovation activity and its effectiveness of these companies. However, that did not happen. The increasing share of innovative products compared with it in the mid-00s was not proportional to the subsidies surge.

What made the situation even more difficult was the level of innovation efficiency of these state-owned enterprises. It is worth noting that the supremacy of Federal ownership over private property had always been "broken" when one tried measuring the innovation efficiency on Meso 2 calculated as the value of the innovative product per employee. However, this "defect" turned out to be very significant in 2013-2014. If the meaning of this indicator for federal ownership enterprises had been 60-70% of the national average in 2004-2005, it dropped to 12-15% of the average in 2013-2014.

As it follows from the above, the policy measures should be aimed at the following components.

- Forcing the enterprises of private and mixed ownership to innovate, for example, by developing competitive processes in relevant markets.
- Reforming the management of state-owned enterprises.
- Increasing the share of enterprises of foreign and joint ownership in the manufacturing industry, for instance, by creating a favourable investment and business climate.

4. Conclusion and discussion of the results

Thus, the meso trajectory can be presented as a sequential process of performing core NIS functions on the different its phases. The role of public policy in these phases is critical.

The study of the problems of regulating the meso-trajectory should take into account that the focus must be on the impact of policies on two groups of factors. The first is external factors whose action is manifested in the existence of high risks and uncertainties distributed over different stages of the meso trajectory. The high risks and uncertainties generate strong disincentives to perform core NIS function. The second group occurs within the meso populations. Some actors of these populations shape it. They can be teemed into factor-forming populations.

Regarding the first group of factors, two conclusions can be drawn. First, government policy that aims to mitigate inherent risks and uncertainties must be dual. It means that, on the one hand, the innovation system should facilitate compensation for a part of uncertainties and risks inherent in innovation activity, and, on the other hand, make the actors carry a significant portion of risks themselves. Secondly, if the NIS is intended for regulating the effects of externalities (e.g. technological spillover) on different phases of the trajectory, then its task is to reduce risks of their adverse influence on the evolutionary trajectories. In this case, the policy should maintain some balance of these influences on different NIS core functions on meso trajectories. Notably, it could provide a choice between a strong or weak public support of intellectual property rights.

The actions of factor-forming populations also contribute to realising the core NIS functions on the different phases of trajectory. The task of monitoring and regulating these actions is highly relevant. To carry out the task, it is necessary to reveal a factor that has had a significant impact on the evolutionary trajectory and consider it as a (hierarchical) system of its attributes. Next, the types of actors that carry the factor attributes should be united in separate populations. The populations should have a property of atomicity and represent the nonintersecting sets of the sample.

Further, it is worthwhile to organise support and expansion of those factoring-forming populations that have a positive effect on the phases of meso trajectories. If the factor-forming population harms the trajectory phases, then the targeted policy should neutralise it, in particular, weakening this actors' population. In the case, when a factor-forming population demonstrates both positive and negative influence on the trajectory, the policy should facilitate a transformation of the actors' behavioural models dominated in the population. It means that it may assist in strengthening the useful parameters of the models and eliminating or smoothing their harmful ones.

The analysis of the dynamics of some factor-forming populations in Russia allows us to display, to some extent, these statements. Therefore, when analysing the resource capacity of enterprises, it was shown that two types of factor-forming populations (populations of small and medium enterprises and those of large enterprises) have some features that could be useful for the development of the innovation trajectory while other their attributes might be harmful to its development. The populations of small and medium enterprises had primary positive innovative attributes. For this reason, the populations need increasing and supporting by the state. As for large enterprises, the public policy should address to overcoming their innovative passivity and neutralise their anticompetitive effects on the markets.

While analysing the factor-forming populations identified by belonging their enterprises to a particular type of property, the population of state-owned enterprises has been taken as an object for public governance. Unfortunately, in the past period, the public governance of this population can not be considered as a rational one. The policy mistake was, in our opinion, that the large-scale government financial injections into innovation expenditures of the companies had not been accompanied by the measures of improving the existing model of innovative behaviour inside the population. In other words, the first purpose and action of public policy had to be changing the dominating model of the innovative practice of the population.

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